

Motivation as a Redemptive Management Tool in Tertiary Education for Smart Green School Programme

Veronica Mogboh (Ph. D.)¹, Nnamdi N. S. Ene (Ph. D.)², & Hilda Agusiobo (Ph. D.)³

Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Godfrey Okoye University Enugu, Nigeria

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Abstract

The central forte in developmental society is realised as a residual product of motivational trajectory. It is sought ardently because it attends to the possibility of accomplishing the goals set for individuals, organisations and the society irrespective of circumstantial difficulties. It is this force which psychologically governs many of our actions and give substance to our achievements. Without motivation, carrying out major beneficial societal projects will be difficult to attain. Thus, the main objective of this paper is to investigate the extent the pursuit of motivation in a school environment can be considered as a redemptive management tool in tertiary education. This paper explored the multifaceted dimensions of motivation as a redemptive management tool in tertiary education delving into its advantages and the potential applications. It is a fact that motivation is a detailed and controlled use of resources to achieve goals, therefore this exploratory paper sought to elucidate the multifaceted impact of motivation as a redemptive forte in education and the strategic management approaches necessary for its successful integration in tertiary education

Keywords: Motivation, education, management, redemptive, circumstantial

Introduction

Motivation in a school environment has been studied for a long time because it also constitutes a determining factor of several academic variables. It would be closely linked to the perseverance of students, their commitment and their curiosity, but also their success. Particularly in higher education, student motivation is a variable to take into consideration since it influences students in their decision to whether or not to pursue courses in a specific field. (Harackiewicz *et al.*, (2020). The problem of student motivation does not present itself in the same way at university as at secondary school. While a large number of students suffer from demotivation upon entering high school, university students generally enter university with strong motivation. However, this decreases over the years.

In fact, if when a closer look is taken at the statistics it can be seen that during the first year of study, a large number of students drop out, change fields, or fail to achieve their goals fixed. Added to this is the fact that the theme of motivation allows both psychology and education to be linked. The objective of this research is therefore to analyse the various tools offered during training from the angle of motivation: what type of motivation can they bring? To which extent motivation can be considered as a redemptive management tool in tertiary education? The goal is to find ideas that would reduce the proportion of failures and dropouts among university students. The work is

presented as follows: after a theoretical introduction which will clarify the different concepts of motivation theories, we will define some variables which, according to various authors in the field, influence motivation. Then, we will see how to insert these different variables into the practice of teaching at the University.

Indeed, for Educators motivation is a sine qua non for their productivity to be appreciatively maintained especially where and when the multiplicity and fecundities of knowledge make the profession perilous and ambitious in galloping developmental pace. In tertiary education some of our students see themselves through the education system as entities devoid of taste and testament for what they perform, and barely get through their time in class. Conceptually they are demotivated even stagnated by the curriculum sometimes by default or purely by dismay, they gradually move towards truancy other forms of delinquency leaving or dropping out of school. Thus, the question retained as the main objective of this research which is to what extent can the pursuit of motivation in a school environment promote students' success in the education?

Definition of Concepts

Motivation

Motivation is derived from the word “motive” which translates into needs, desires, wants and energy in people to be continually interested and committed to do a job, play a role, study a subject, or to try to attain a goal. For example, a student spends extra time researching because he wants better grades in class or gain more insight into a particular them. From the point of view of philosophy, “motivation is the action to motivate, to allege the considerations which serve as reason(s) before the act and justification for this act, a posteriori”. In psychology, “motivation is seen as the set of dynamic factors which direct the action of an individual towards a given goal, which determine his behaviour and provoke a given behaviour in him or modify the pattern of his present behaviour”. In the educational psychology sector, “the motivation is the set of dynamic factors which arouse in a student or a group of students the desire to learn. Ryan *et al* (2020). Thus, according to Vallerand and Thill (1993) cited by Rolland Viau (2013), researchers in social psychology and specialists in motivation “the concept of motivation represents the hypothetical construct used to describe the internal and/or external forces producing the triggering, direction, intensity and persistence of behaviour”

Education

Education is the right of every individual and is given in formal, informal and non-formal templates as a form of integration, assimilation and inculturation into the society. Basically, education revolves on the ever-changing values of world social culture. Each era of world history produced its own values which are incorporated into the society through appropriate processes and procedures. Marzano *et al.*, (2015). Our present world culture is both innovative and competitive having a global village lifestyle that enhances volunteerism ethos. The challenge of this globalised lifestyle has upturned most processes and procedures in the society making a demand of educational techniques, production and consumption patterns. It is necessary that education should be proactive in its content and rendition to maintain its relative concepts in development.

Management

According to Robinson *et al* (2017), management is the process of planning, organizing, directing and controlling resources (human, financial, physical, and informational) to achieve organizational goals efficiently and effectively. It involves coordinating the efforts of people to achieve specific objectives. It involves various functions such as decision making, leadership, and communication within an organisation. In summary, management is the entire work done to put into effectively use the human and material resources to achieve organisational aims and objectives. In the context of education, management refers to the systematic and strategic organisation, coordination, and administration of educational resources and processes to achieve the goals and objectives of an educational institution. Bush *et al* (2012) opines that management encompasses planning and overseeing the allocation of human, financial and physical resources to ensure the delivery of educational services. Educational management involves a range of responsibilities, including curriculum development, staff supervision, student welfare, and community engagement, all aimed at fostering an optimal learning environment.

Motivation and Smart Green Schools Programme

Without motivation, there will be no action and no learning. We therefore understand the importance, both for students and for teachers. Indeed, by helping the students feel more motivated in school, they would be more involved in their own education and, consequently, they would be more likely to succeed. In these circumstances, motivation would appear for the teachers in charge, as a goal to reach, and a precious tool to ensure the success of the pedagogical approaches. Motivation according to Viau (2009), could then be perceived as a key to fight against school dropout and failure. The latter is also a concern for institutions concerned with support learning and reduce dropouts and failures: strengthening motivation is one of the support measures favoured by institutions that want not only to support their students' learning, but also to reduce dropouts and failures often attributable to problems of demotivation and, consequently, disengagement from studies. The role therefore of a teacher is to arouse interest in performance by students. So, teacher should make it a point of duty to impress on them that hard work really pays irrespective of some obnoxious government policies that borders on favouritism and unethical dimension.

Therefore, it is a question of positive motivation and not negative motivation. In fact, some of our education policies do not portray ethical equity and reactions occur in corruptive tendency. These are present in both teaching and learning communes. When a teacher feels he is not adequately and properly rewarded for proven efforts, he feels cheated and fights the system through lowering of standards by engaging in other negative agenda, upholds aggrandisements in ethical / nonethical forms etc. students equally look out for easy passage to get the almighty paper certification without qualification, honour and character. So, education is a motivational factorised instrument which is heavily relied on to bring our society out of the woods of ignorance, disease and the decadence of corruptive tendencies and actions.

Motivational Constructs in Tertiary Education

As said before, motivation is a very important element in tertiary education because it helps students to become more active and successful. One of the gateways offered to teachers to maintain the motivation of their students is the educational activities that they offer them. These activities must have a positive influence on the value that students attach to them (perception of usefulness), on their perception of their competence to carry them out and on their feeling of controllability of their progress.

So, a teacher must give students the opportunity to express their point of view on a learning situation (for example what solution should they consider to solve the problem posed?), provide explanations (for example explaining the interest of a learning situation), recognize and accept difficulties and expressions of negative affect (for example, show empathy by recognizing that a situation may be difficult or frustrating), offer real choices taking into account preferences and interests, use informational and flexible language, communicate clear goals and content, propose tasks adapted to the possibilities of each person, with a challenge to overcome, provide solutions and advice to enable students to progress, deliver positive feedback (e.g. highlight the positive aspects of any attempt: “that’s good, you tried”), pay attention, invest time and energy in interactions (e.g. take the time to discuss with students, show that you believe in their development potential), express affection, understanding, show respect, use humour and promote conviviality.

Management Strategies to Enhance Effective Motivation of Students

Teachers could consider that they have little influence on student motivation in the sense that it depends on multiple factors over which they do not necessarily have control. However, they have real levers likely to promote quality motivation:

- Nurture basic psychological needs.
- Act on the motivational climate of a course.
- Adapt the teaching style.

Nurture Basic Psychological Needs

According to self-determination theory, Deci and Ryan, (1991, 2000), fostering quality motivation requires that three fundamental psychological needs be satisfied: the needs for autonomy, social proximity and competence.

- The need for autonomy refers to the need to do choices and being at the origin of its activities and objectives. The individual engages and acts on his environment according to its own decisions. For Viau (2009), the perception of controllability which can be linked to the need for autonomy is defined by the degree of control a student believes they exercise on the progress of an activity. If they have the feeling that everything is decided in advance and that there is no All that remains for them to do is follow their motivational dynamics in will suffer.
- The need for social proximity concerns the desire to feel accepted and experience good social relationships. There student's perception of social proximity refers to the feeling that he has to be respected, integrated and close to the teacher and others group members.
- The need for competence reflects the desire to experience efficiency. In a learning context, perception that the student has of his competence is the judgment he makes on their ability to

adequately succeed in the educational activity which is offered to him. People's perceptions of their ability are better predictors of their behavior than their real capabilities.

According to Viau's model, the motivational dynamics of a student (in addition to the factors of competence and autonomy/controllability) also finds its source in the perception that the proposed activity has value, that it makes sense. This will be the case, for example, for a student wishing to work in the environmental field to whom we offer activities relating to ecology. For a student to perceive the value of an activity, it is desirable that he judges it to be both interesting and useful

Act on the Motivational Climate

Many factors positively or negatively influence student experiences. One of these factors is the motivational climate that the teacher establishes Ryan and Deci (2020). The motivational climate corresponds to the psychological environment of the class, the atmosphere which guides the goals and motivations of students. It is created by what teachers say and do, how they organize lessons and communicate.

By the behaviours he implements, the learning activities he offers, the nature of his interactions with students, the psychological climate that he develops, the feedback he delivers, the teacher is likely to "make a difference", in terms of learning and more generally the academic success of students. Research has also quantified this "teacher effect" whose weight is estimated at around 16% on educational acquisitions. Climate is affected in particular by why, when and how teachers feedback. Thus, a teacher who emphasizes the positive points, provides advice for progress and encourages his students, establishes a more supportive motivational climate than one who provides little feedback or systematically negative or inconsistent feedback.

Adapt the Teaching Style

Teaching style is an important determinant of motivational climate. Style is the characteristic manner in which a teacher conducts interactions with students". It is defined by Fraissinhe and Gallaup (2021) "as a series of operations through which the teacher selects and manages classifies tasks, materials, and student activities." But beyond these technical aspects, the teaching style mobilizes what is at the heart of teachers' values, beliefs and habitual behaviors and manifests itself in response to questions such as: what is important when I teach? What do I want to convey to students? What are for me, the indicators of a good teacher? What are the main values that guide me? The teaching style leads to the deployment of certain teaching practices which, supporting the psychological needs fundamentals of students, are likely to have a positive influence on their motivation. Pedagogical practices make a difference on perseverance and success in higher education. Indeed, certain practices pedagogical tools used by teachers can constitute a small step for the perseverance of some students, while others prove to be real strides.

Management Strategies for Motivation of Teachers for Effective Teaching / Learning

Around the world, the conversation about teachers is changing. While the responsibility of teachers has until now been at the forefront, in recent years there has been an increasing emphasis on ways to better support, motivate and professionalize them. Gallaup *et al* (2021) opined that to sustain the motivation of teachers and school leaders, they need spaces where they can train, interact and

collaborate professionally, and where they can speak freely without feeling judged or supervised. Teachers and school leaders need the recognition and esteem of their students, but also of the society in which they work: motivation must therefore be constantly nourished, not only at school but also more broadly, at the system level.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

Motivation is one of the most important factors in academic success. At the same time, research shows that engagement is, from the start of a child's school career, one of the main indicators of the risk of dropping out of school. A motivated student will be willing to commit and make efforts, which will allow them to learn more sustainably, achieve better academic results and persevere more.

All this research carried out on motivation allows us to glimpse numerous perspectives of reflection to promote the academic success of students. In fact, some students are gradually abandoning school. Others report growing boredom in class, where they adopt a passive, demobilized attitude. Due to lack of motivation, academic results are declining, and sometimes lead to failure. Among the factors to consider here, those which interested us in particular relate mainly to the university framework and therefore to what education professionals can undertake in order to reverse the trend. Viau (2009) stated that being a teacher requires being able to renew one's knowledge, evaluate the effectiveness of one's practice and keep oneself regularly informed of both disciplinary and socio-pedagogical advances.

In fact, when it comes to the question of motivation, we must put in place specific strategies to (re)generate it in our students who have dropped out or resigned, and to maintain it for our dynamic students. So, motivation problems at university should be approached from the perspective of maintenance, the efforts that must be devoted to helping students maintain strong motivation throughout their studies. Finally, we must not lose sight of the fact that there are other entry points to achieve student motivation, notably the evaluative practices of teachers, and themselves, through their attitudes and their relationships with students.

Recommendations

Tertiary education needs to be practicalized to engage the student's interest and desire to learn in consonance with their enquiring nature. Teachers should be regularly sensitized and encouraged to be committed and responsible in their role. Constant supervision is an imperative tool in motivation that is beneficial to both student and teachers for proper implementation of tertiary education programme. The main entry points offered to teachers to maintain the motivation of their students are: the educational activities they offer them, their evaluative practices as teachers and the climate of the class. These factors over which teachers have power must have a positive influence on the value that students place on educational activities that will allow them to learn (perception of usefulness), their perception of competence to accomplish them and their feeling of controllability on their progress.

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